

Instagram Coffee Shop Content Ideation for Pondok Aren (Bintaro) Community

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ABSTRACT: The development of the coffee shop industry in Bintaro, South Tangerang is becoming more numerous and varied, this has given rise to competition for customers. Therefore coffee shops carry out Instagram activities as a channel to provide their content. However, 77.22% of coffee shops are dissatisfied with the performance of their Instagram. In the final project this aims to find out what content attracts the Bintaro Community and how this content influences brand equity. This study uses the PLS method with the independent variable Instagram Attractiveness (IA) and the dependent variables in the form of Brand Awareness (BA), Brand Image (BI), Perceived Quality (PQ), Brand Love (BL) and Brand Re-usage Intention (RI). Data collection used the Google form which was distributed to 210 respondents from the Bintaro community who use Instagram.

From the results of the study, it was found that the Instagram Attractiveness variable was accepted and had a positive impact on Brand Awareness, Brand Image, Perceived Quality. Brand Awareness, Brand Image, Perceived Quality variables were accepted and had a positive impact on Brand Love and Brand Re-usage Intention. However, the Brand Awareness variable for Brand Re-usage Intention is rejected. It can be concluded that Menu, Ambience and Event content at coffee shops are attractive types of content and will have a positive impact on Brand Equity. The solutions given to coffee shops are planning, creating, and also posting menu content, events and also ambience with viral marketing strategies, building Instagram themes for brand images, and also using photography techniques to create content.

KEYWORDS: Brand Equity, Coffee shop, Content Ideation, Instagram, Marketing

INTRODUCTION

In addition to the expansion of the coffee business in Indonesia, the number of coffee shops has increased. It is common for coffee shops to be located close to one another. Several coffee shops are located in the Pondok Aren subdistrict, also known as Bintaro, in South Tangerang. The magnitude of the coffee shop sector in Bintaro necessitates that coffee shops execute a sustainable business plan. Numerous marketing methods are frequently employed to lure customers to coffee businesses. Instagram is one of the technologies they utilize. Instagram is a social networking platform for sharing photographs and videos. They also utilized Instagram to promote their establishment and food. However, many coffee businesses struggle to manage their own Instagram accounts. Both between their discontent with the performance of the uploaded content and their lack of intriguing ideas for the future upload.

After further review, as many as 72.22% of coffee shops in Bintaro do not have the expected interactions (like, comment, save and share) with their target audience, then 16.67% of coffee shops have not reached the target followers they want and 11.11% have not actively posted either on Instagram feeds, reels, and stories. For more details can be seen in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Instagram Coffee Shop Performance Issue

In the research, it was also revealed that 66.67 percent of coffee businesses had trouble managing their Instagram accounts. They have difficulties posting to Instagram for two primary reasons: first, they do not know what material is engaging for their audience and they do not understand how to effectively execute content (62.5%), and second, they do not have the human resources to spend on managing Instagram (37.5%). Consequently, the purpose of this study is to aid the coffee shop business in Bintaro in developing content based on the preferences of the Bintaro community in order to create brand equity.

Research Questions and Research Objectives

In this final project, it is necessary to have a research question as the initial foundation for carrying out this research. The research question is as follows:

1. What Instagram content attracts Bintaro people to the coffee shop industry?
2. How does coffee shop's Instagram content affect Instagram's brand equity?

Based on the research question above, then the research objectives as follows:

1. Find out attractive Instagram content for Bintaro people towards the coffee shop industry
2. Knowing how Instagram content affects Instagram's brand equity.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Brand Awareness

Brand awareness is defined as the performance of brand recognition and brand recall. The primary objective is to establish a strong brand image through long-lasting, brand-resonant relationships. Recall of a brand is the ability of consumers to retrieve the brand from memory when presented with the product category, the needs served by the category, a purchase, or a circumstance involving a habit. Customers' ability to confirm prior exposure to a brand when presented with the brand as a cue is the definition of brand recognition [1]. Brand recognition is a continuum ranging from a nebulous perception that the brand is well-known to the conviction that it is the only competitor in its product category. Despite the fact that the concept of brand equity, of which brand awareness is one of the important components, has been exposed and cemented in the specialized literature over the last few decades, the term has been and continues to be handled in a variety of ways [2].

Figure 2. The Awareness Pyramid

Brand Image

Brand awareness is a vital first step in constructing brand equity, but it is usually insufficient. The great majority of customers, in the vast majority of cases, also evaluate other variables, such as the brand's meaning or image. Improving a brand's image demands giving it meaning in the eyes of consumers and expressing what it should stand for. The brand may produce several connotations, some of which are commonly connected with more utilitarian, performance-related criteria and others with more ethereal, imagery-related characteristics. Strong, positive, and distinctive brand relationships are particularly critical for building brand equity [1].

Perceived Quality

Perceptions of a product's quality are customers' ideas regarding the product's perceived quality. Perceived quality refers to how customers as a whole assess generally accepted manufacturing practices [3]. Perceived quality refers to the consumer's perception of the product or service's quality [4]. Regarding consumer brand engagement, customers' perceptions of the dependability and dependability of a product or service are strongly correlated with their preferences, level of satisfaction, and purchase decisions [5].

Brand Love

Brand love refers to the degree of emotional affinity pleased customers have for a certain brand. It includes emotional demonstrations of affection, brand dedication and passion, loyalty, and positive word-of-mouth. Multiple brands may be identified and preferred by consumers. However, individuals can only feel powerful "love-like" emotions for a limited number of companies. Love is a metaphor for consumer feelings and behaviors that transcend fundamental loyalty. Therefore, brand love is incomparable since it is a stronger and more enduring emotion than brand liking. In other words, brand love is stronger on an emotional level. Conceptually, brand love is distinct from other brand-related concepts such as "brand joy." Customers may develop feelings of fondness for a brand, hence elevating its perceived worth [6].

Brand Re-Usage Intention

A user's opinion of a service affects their desire to use it, which in turn affects the service's sustainability. The concept of re-usage intention indicates the desire of a consumer to employ a product or service again. It is also the degree to which a consumer subjectively prefers to return to and promote a service to others. Thus, re-usage intent is conceptually like the marketing notion of customer loyalty. This shows that the intention to repurchase reflects consumer loyalty. Current marketing study indicates that a product's or service's success is contingent on its continued use. This study defined brand Instagram re-usage intention as the likelihood of using a brand's Instagram account in the future [6].

Co-Creation Modelling

Co-creation is the process through which a firm and a client together develop value. The corporation makes no attempt to gain the customer's favor. Allowing the customer to collaborate in the creation of a service experience that suits her demands. Developing an environment for experiences in which users can actively converse and co-create personalized ones; the product may be same (such as Lego Mindstorms), but users can construct unique ones. Companies view customer relationship management as the selection and management of the "right" clients. The exchange is the hub for commercial activity and economic value extraction.

Customers and business interactions are not considered sources of value creation [7]. Value exchange and extraction are essentially the responsibility of the market, which is distinct from the value generation process. As the market is a location where value is exchanged and the customer must be persuaded for the firm to maximize transactional value, it is not surprising that the flow of communications is also from the corporate to the consumer [8].

Conceptual Framework

Conceptual framework is a system to find out a certain phenomenon that is sought. The following can be seen in **Figure 3** the conceptual framework used in this research.

Figure 3. Conceptual Framework

Marketing activities will have a positive effect on customer-based brand equity. The modification made by the author is menu, ambience, and event content with interaction, entertainment, trendiness set as parameter of Instagram Attractiveness.

- H1: Instagram attractiveness has a positive impact on Instagram brand awareness
- H2: Instagram attractiveness has a positive impact on Instagram brand image
- H3: Instagram attractiveness has a positive impact on Instagram perceived quality
- H4: Instagram brand awareness has a positive impact on Instagram brand love
- H5: Instagram brand image has a positive impact on Instagram brand love
- H6: Instagram perceived quality has a positive impact on Instagram brand love
- H7: Instagram brand awareness has a positive impact on brand Instagram re-usage intention
- H8: Instagram brand image has a positive impact on brand Instagram re-usage intention
- H9: Instagram perceived quality has a positive impact on brand Instagram re-usage intention.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The research design of this final project is started by identifies the coffee shop Industry in Bintaro. Preliminary questionnaire is given out to coffee shops to be find what problem they are facing towards their Instagram performance. The results of the preliminary questionnaire will be analyzed to find the problem statement. After obtaining the problem statement experienced by the coffee shop in Bintaro, it is continued with the objective writing of this final project. With the research objective of writing this final project, it is followed by data collection using a questionnaire that is distributed to the people of Bintaro related to the conceptual framework

that has been listed. after getting the data then analyzed using PLS-SEM. Based on the data that has been analyzed, a strategy formulation will be carried out to find the best solution that can be done by coffee shops in Bintaro for Instagram content ideation. Finally, the conclusion and recommendations. The research design framework can be seen in the **Figure 4**.

Figure 4. Research Design

Data Collection

A. Observation

The author makes an observation towards coffee shop industry in Bintaro. Meanwhile, observations were made by looking for an integrated coffee shop that has Instagram in the coffee shop and seeing what content is created by them. Besides that, the author also observes the performance of the content created by looking at the number of likes and comments on several posts.

B. Questionnaire

A questionnaire is a type of data collecting in which a set of statements or concerns are written to the responder for them to answer to user requests [9]. Data collection based on a questionnaire was carried out 2 times, namely in the preliminary and in the research section of the Bintaro community. In the preliminary questionnaire, data was collected based on short answers so that each coffee shop could elaborate on the problems related to the performance of the Instagram they handled.

In this study, a questionnaire was utilized to determine Instagram content ideas for coffee shops based on co-creation modelling with the Bintaro community to promote customer-based brand equity, which consists of 48 statement items and their appropriateness with the conceptual framework employed. The questionnaire contains a 1-5 scale based on their level of agreement with the questions. While the questionnaire for content ideation was distributed to 200 respondents from Bintaro, South Tangerang as a sample of this research. The questionnaire list can be seen in **Table 2**.

Data Processing

Validity and Reliability Test

Validity is the most important consideration in test evaluation. The concept refers to the appropriateness, meaningfulness and usefulness of the specific inferences made from test scores. Test validation is the process of accumulating evidence to support such inferences. A variety of inferences may be made from scores produced by a given test, and there are many ways of accumulating evidence to support any in-ference [10]. On the validity test, the author distributed questionnaires to 30 respondents. So that the validity test was obtained with the Pearson correlation score at R table 0.361 with a significance level of 5%

PLS-SEM

According to its definition, PLS is a technique that works well for exploratory modelling or other research tasks like prediction. Covariance-based SEM is used when confirmatory modelling is the research's primary objective. In PLS-SEM models, some variables may have an impact on others while still acting as causes of other variables later in the proposed causal chain. The questionnaire for PLS-SEM analysis is given to 200 respondents that are live or work in Pondok Aren (Bintaro) area. The distribution will be on @bintaro.brews Instagram which are Bintaro Coffee Shop content creator in Bintaro and the Author personal Instagram. The data collected will be analysed by SMART PLS tool.

Study Context

In this section, we will explain demographic segmentation and respondent behavior towards Instagram coffee shops in Bintaro. This is done to get a more specific description of the respondent. The data obtained will also be used as a reference for the discussion. Demographic data can be seen from **Figure 5 and Figure 6**

Figure 5. Respondence Gender

Figure 6. Residence Age

The demographic data that we can see from **Figures 5 and 6** are data that can be used as a reference for selecting preferred content preferences in terms of Gender and Age. In addition, behavioral data regarding the current situation regarding the number of respondents who have followed the Instagram coffee shop in Bintaro and what they are looking for on the Instagram coffee shop are also obtained. Behavior data can be seen in **Figure 7** and **Figure 8**.

Figure 7. Number of Bintaro Coffee Shop Followed by Respondent

Figure 8. Coffee Shop Most Searched Content

In **Figure 7** we can see that the majority of the respondents followed at least 1 coffee shop in Bintaro and only 19% did not follow any coffee shop. Whereas in **Figure 8** we can see that most respondents are looking for information related to information from the Ambience store. In addition, respondents also looked for content from menus, promos or discounts, operating hours, and event content at coffee shops in Bintaro.

Loading Factor

A loading factor is a figure that illustrates the relationship between a question item's score and the rating of the construct indicators used to measure the construct. A valid loading factor is one that is more than 0.7. First inspection of the matrix loading factor, a loading factor of around 0.3 is seen to have reached the minimal threshold, a loading factor of about 0.4 is thought to be better, and a loading factor of more than 0.5 is typically thought to be substantial [11]. Therefore, author choose 0,7 as the best rating of the loading factor. The results of the loading factor can be seen in **Table 1** after the data has been processed using Smart-PLS.

Table I. Loading Factor

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Brand Awareness</i>	<i>Brand Image</i>	<i>Brand Love</i>	<i>Instagram Attractiveness</i>	<i>Perceived Quality</i>	<i>Re-usage Intention</i>
BA1	0.801					
BA2	0.827					
BA3	0.754					
BI1		0.811				
BI2		0.829				
BI3		0.786				
BL1			0.776			
BL3			0.771			
BL4			0.820			
BL6			0.888			
BL7			0.879			
BL9			0.895			
IA4				0.770		
IA5				0.725		
IA6				0.744		
IA7				0.795		
IA8				0.721		
IA9				0.751		
PQ1					0.917	
PQ2					0.920	
RI1						0.728
RI3						0.773
RI4						0.815

RI5					0.801
RI6					0.872
RI7					0.844
RI8					0.869
RI9					0.837

Source: Author's Research

Based on the **Table I** above, all the loading factor score is above 0.7 after the second iteration and it can be concluded that the indicators are valid. Previously there were several invalid indicators, these indicators were BL2, BL8, IA1, IA2, IA3, PQ3, and RI2. This decreased on indicators are recommended by [11] which stated that if the loading factor (lf) must be > 0.7, if not it can be deleted. This shows that the answers related to the questions presented to the respondents are too varied. So, there is no pattern that can be observed.

Average Variance Extracted

The degree to which a construct differs from other constructs is measured by its discriminant validity. A construct is shown to be distinct and capable of capturing the phenomena being measured if its discriminant validity score is high. Comparing the square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) or the correlation coefficient between the constructs is one technique to assess it [11]. The results of the AVE calculation using Smart-PLS can be seen in **Table 3**.

Table II. Convergent Validity

Indicator	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Brand Awareness	0.707	0.837	0.631
Brand Image	0.738	0.850	0.654
Brand Love	0.915	0.935	0.705
Instagram Attractiveness	0.846	0.886	0.565
Perceived Quality	0.815	0.915	0.844
Re-usage Intention	0.929	0.942	0.670

Source: Author's Design

We can observe from the table above that the Average Variance value obtained via Smart PLS is more than 0.5. Therefore, it may be said that the report's variable indicators are reliable. A value of ≥ 0.50 is the suggested range for the variance extracted value [11]. The use of AVE as a criterion for evaluating convergent validity is advised by [12] a decent indicator of convergent validity is an AVE of at least 0.5. In other words, latent variables may often account for more than 50% of the variation of the indicators.

Based on **Table II** it also can be concluded that based on Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability that the indicators are reliable because the score is ≥ 0.7 . The Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability is accepted and if its ≥ 0.8 the result is very satisfying.

Therefore, all the indicators are acceptable and for the indicator of Brand love, Instagram Attractiveness, Perceived Quality, and Re-usage intention are very satisfying [11].

Cross-loading Factor

Cross loading is measured by comparing the correlation of indicators with their respective blocks' and other blocks' constructions. If the correlation between the indicator and the construct is greater than the correlation with the other block constructions, this suggests that the construct is more effective than the others at reducing the size of their block [11]. Cross-loading Factor can be seen in **Table III**.

Table III. Cross-loading Factor

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Brand Awareness</i>	<i>Brand Image</i>	<i>Brand Love</i>	<i>Instagram Attractiveness</i>	<i>Perceived Quality</i>	<i>Re-usage Intention</i>
BA1	0.801	0.455	0.466	0.556	0.363	0.270
BA2	0.827	0.591	0.478	0.463	0.455	0.359
BA3	0.754	0.490	0.395	0.489	0.414	0.427
BI1	0.499	0.811	0.614	0.434	0.519	0.385
BI2	0.560	0.829	0.598	0.373	0.664	0.522
BI3	0.502	0.786	0.475	0.241	0.513	0.422
BL1	0.491	0.551	0.776	0.497	0.497	0.552
BL3	0.422	0.487	0.771	0.353	0.452	0.586
BL4	0.445	0.575	0.820	0.421	0.442	0.531
BL6	0.446	0.616	0.888	0.425	0.540	0.638
BL7	0.506	0.664	0.879	0.421	0.558	0.584
BL9	0.514	0.623	0.895	0.509	0.579	0.619
IA4	0.448	0.341	0.391	0.770	0.307	0.341
IA5	0.393	0.291	0.353	0.725	0.321	0.423
IA6	0.436	0.298	0.386	0.744	0.300	0.346
IA7	0.589	0.374	0.421	0.795	0.319	0.244
IA8	0.474	0.317	0.357	0.721	0.293	0.420
IA9	0.490	0.355	0.441	0.751	0.297	0.248
PQ1	0.498	0.651	0.548	0.380	0.917	0.529
PQ2	0.453	0.642	0.577	0.368	0.920	0.532
RI1	0.346	0.384	0.526	0.252	0.409	0.728
RI3	0.344	0.453	0.550	0.285	0.427	0.773
RI4	0.432	0.496	0.601	0.367	0.528	0.815
RI5	0.270	0.364	0.504	0.366	0.458	0.801
RI6	0.350	0.428	0.616	0.386	0.445	0.872
RI7	0.362	0.481	0.531	0.366	0.518	0.844
RI8	0.352	0.443	0.598	0.444	0.486	0.869
RI9	0.419	0.523	0.621	0.402	0.489	0.837

Source: Author’s Design

According to **Table III** all indicators have higher correlation coefficients with each construct than the score of the indicator correlation coefficient with in construct block in the opposite column. Thus, it may be said that each block indication is a component of the inner construct column. This is in accordance with [11] where each constituent component of the construct must have a higher value than the other columns.

Structural Model (Inner Model)

The structural model, also known as the inner model, is evaluated after the construct/variable measurement model has been assessed. The first stage is to assess the model's structural integrity by considering the importance of the connections between the constructs and variables. This is evident from the route coefficient, which expresses how strongly the link between the constructs is related to one another. The route coefficient's sign or direction must align with the proposed theory; the significance may be demonstrated in the t test or C.R (critical ratio) resulted by the bootstrapping or resampling procedure approach [11]. The structural model table that consists of path coefficient, T-Statistic (t-test), and P-Value can be seen in **Table IV**.

Table IV. Structural Model

Variable	Path Coefficient	T-Statistics	P-Value	Hypothesis	Result
IA-BA	0.633	10.339	0.000	H1	ACCEPTED
IA-BI	0.441	5.238	0.000	H2	ACCEPTED
IA-PQ	0.407	5.393	0.000	H3	ACCEPTED
BA-BL	0.165	2.159	0.031	H4	ACCEPTED
BI-BL	0.445	5.232	0.000	H5	ACCEPTED
PQ-BL	0.214	2.787	0.006	H6	ACCEPTED
BA-RI	0.111	1.331	0.184	H7	REJECTED
BI-RI	0.222	2.037	0.042	H8	ACCEPTED
PQ-RI	0.364	4.473	0.000	H9	ACCEPTED

Source: Author’s Design

Path Coefficient

Based on **Table IV** from the Path Coefficient column, we can see the relationship between variables. The Instagram Attractiveness variable on Brand Awareness shows that the influence is 0.633 units, on Instagram Attractiveness on Brand Image it has an influence of 0.441 units, on Instagram Attractiveness on Perceived Quality is 0.407, on Brand Awareness on Brand Love is 0.165, on Brand Image on Brand Love is 0.445, on Perceived Quality on Brand Love is 0.214, on Brand Awareness on Re-usage Intention is 0.111, on Brand Image on Re-usage Intention is 0.222, and on Perceived Quality on Re-usage Intention is 0.364. Then the value of the path coefficient is tested for significance with the t-statistic and p-value. Path coefficient graph can be seen in **Figure 9**.

Figure 9. Path Coefficient of PLS-SEM

T-statistic and P-Value

From the t-statistic and p-value column in **Table IV** we can perform hypothesis testing using confidence level of 95% with t-table of 1.96 and p-value < 0.05 , hypothesis testing as follows:

Hypothesis 1: Instagram Attractiveness (IA) is accepted and has significant effect on Brand Awareness (BA). The t-statistic value is $10,339 \geq 1.96$ and the p-value is $0.000 \leq 0.05$.

Hypothesis 2: Instagram Attractiveness (IA) is accepted and has significant effect on Brand Image (BI). The t-statistic value is $5.238 \geq 1.96$ and the p-value is $0.000 \leq 0.05$.

Hypothesis 3: Instagram Attractiveness (IA) is accepted and has significant effect on Perceived Quality (PQ). The t-statistic value is $5,393 \geq 1.96$ and the p-value is $0.000 \leq 0.05$.

Hypothesis 4: Brand Awareness (BA) is accepted and has significant effect on Brand Love (BL). The t-statistic value is $2.159 \geq 1.96$ and the p-value is $0.031 \leq 0.05$.

Hypothesis 5: Brand Image (BI) is accepted and has significant effect on Brand Love (BL). The t-statistic value is $5.232 \geq 1.96$ and the p-value is $0.000 \leq 0.05$.

Hypothesis 6: Perceived Quality (PQ) is accepted and has significant effect on Brand Love (BL). The t-statistic value is $2,787 \geq 1.96$ and the p-value is $0.006 \leq 0.05$.

Hypothesis 7: Brand Awareness (BA) is rejected and has no effect on Re-usage Intention (RI). The t-statistic value is $1.331 \geq 1.96$ and the p-value is $0.184 \geq 0.05$.

Hypothesis 8: Brand Image (BI) is accepted and has significant effect on Re-usage Intention (RI). The t-statistic value is $2.037 \geq 1.96$ p-value is $0.042 \leq 0.05$.

Hypothesis 9: Perceived Quality is accepted and has significant effect on Re-usage Intention (RI). The t-statistic value is $4.473 \geq 1.96$ p-value is $0.000 \leq 0.05$.

Based on the results of the Instagram attractiveness hypothesis on brand awareness, it gets positive and significant results. This is in accordance with research from [12] where Instagram activity on a brand will increase awareness of that brand. Moreover, if the content provided to the audience is implemented by strategies such as paid promotions, Facebook ads, and endorsements. This will increase the exposure of the brand. In addition [13] states that brand awareness is heavily influenced by Instagram activity. This is because to continue to increase awareness, content on Instagram must be able to make the audience use the share feature on Instagram to directly notify other users to check out the brand. Indirectly, interesting Instagram content will make the audience do word-of-mouth marketing so that it reaches more exposure.

In the Instagram attractiveness hypothesis for brand image, it produces positive results and has a significant effect. The results obtained are in accordance with research from [14] where Instagram activity creates a better brand image in coffee shops. The same thing is also discussed in [15], which states that content from Instagram that is attractive and attracts the attention of its audience will create a better brand image, this is because an attractive Instagram creates a strong brand, and is unique and trust in the brand. Based on the results of [6], trendy, entertaining and interactive Instagram coffee shop content will significantly increase customerbased brand equity which directly affects brand awareness, brand image and perceived quality. This result was obtained because the content posted is quality content that can make the audience love it so that they follow the Instagram account to see other and updated coffee shop content.

Based on **Table IV** all the indicator except for the indicator of Brand Awareness - Brand Re-usage Intention. This occurs due to the p-value of BA-RI $0.184 \geq 0.05$ and the t-statistic value is $1.331 < 1.96$. According to [11] the P-value is supposed to be lower than 0.05 in order to be significantly correlated. Therefore it has a positive effect but not significant. This is because even well-known brands have not been able to get their audience to follow the account. They are aware of a particular brand but have no desire to see the content provided by that brand. So, to make a loyal audience with the coffee shop brand, it must be combined with a brand image and also good perceived quality content.

R Squared Value

The next stage is to determine how well the latent variable variation explains the indicator variable once the parameter significance test has been conducted and its significance has been established [17]. The squared multiple correlation coefficient (R^2) is utilized to ascertain the extent to which the variation of the latent variable explains the indicator variable. Q^2 predictive relevance is another criterion in structural measurement that assists to validate the model. This measurement is appropriate if the endogenous latent variable's measurement model is reflective. The R^2 of the indicator can be seen in **Table V**

Table V. R Squared Value

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>R Square</i>	<i>R Square Adjusted</i>	<i>Predictive Relevance (Q^2)</i>
Brand Awareness	0.401	0.398	0.226
Brand Image	0.194	0.190	
Brand Love	0.536	0.529	
Perceived Quality	0.166	0.162	
Re-usage Intention	0.382	0.373	

Source: Author's Design

Based on **Table V** we can conclude that the Brand Awareness indicator has an R^2 value of 0.401, the Brand Image indicator has a value of 0.192, the Brand Love indicator has a value of 0.536, the Perceived Quality indicator has a value of 0.166, and the Reusage Intention indicator has a value of 0.382. Using R Square, the assessment of structural models, according to [16], tries to estimate the proportion of the variation of each endogenous variable in the model that is explained by exogenous variables. R^2 values of 0.25 (strong structural model), 0.45 (moderate structural model), and 0.65 are suggested (low structural model). The R^2 score of less than 0.85 suggests a multicollinearity issue between exogenous variables. Therefore, according to data analysis, the Brand Awareness indicator has a strong-moderate percentage of variance, Brand Image has a strong percentage of variance, Brand love has a moderate-weak percentage of variance, Perceived Quality has a strong percentage of variance, and Re-usage Intention has a high percentage of variance. strong-moderate.

In terms of predictive relevance (Q^2), the obtained value is 0.226. It asserts that predictive relevance assists to validate the model. This measurement is appropriate if the endogenous latent variable's measurement model is reflective. The predictive relevance of Q^2 findings is deemed excellent if the value is greater than 0, which shows that the exogenous latent variable serves as an explanatory variable capable of predicting its endogenous variables [18]. For exogenous latent variables to predict endogenous variables, it may be stated that predictive relevance has a high value.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

Many coffee shops in Bintaro are starting to open for business. This makes it difficult for coffee shops to compete to become the choice of Bintaro community customers. Therefore, coffee shops use Instagram as a promotional tool and media related to their coffee shop. However, 18 out of 24 of coffee shops in Bintaro are not satisfied with the performance of the Instagram they handle, both in terms of engagement, lack of followers, and lack of ideas for creating content for them. This is the main basis of this research.

After conducting research, the Bintaro community's preference for Instagram content was obtained. Research shows that Ambience content and also Event content in coffee shops are attractive content, but for menu content there is an unpredictable pattern because too many people think differently. This is an input for coffee shops to give more importance to Ambience and Event content, even though menu content cannot be abandoned either. So that makes their Instagram coffee shop more attractive.

From an attractive Instagram, coffee shops can get better Brand Awareness, Brand Image, and Perceived Quality. This is evidenced by the existence of a positive and significant correlation between Instagram Attractiveness and other variables. Due to good Brand Awareness, Brand Image, and Perceived Quality, it makes people like the brand. This is evidenced by the existence of a positive correlation between these variables and Brand Love. Finally, if a coffee shop can maintain its Brand Image and Perceived Quality,

eventually the audience will follow their Instagram account. This is evidenced by a positive correlation between these variables and Brand Re-usage Intention.

It can be concluded that to get Brand Love and Brand Re-usage Intention, the first step for a coffee shop is to create Instagram Attractiveness through Ambience, Event and Menu content. Currently, this content can be applied via Instagram Feeds, Reels and also Stories. With the Gant chart that has been provided, it is hoped that coffee shops can get better customer-based brand equity.

Recommendation

Some things that the author recommends for coffee shops are:

1. Using a Viral Marketing Strategy.

In this strategy, the coffee shop can use a trending song and try to make Instagram Reels with that song. This can also be done by collaborating with Coffee Hopper, content creators who take content about coffee shops and have quality and quite a lot of followers. As well as taking advantage of the "share" feature on Instagram by including their personal coffee shop hashtag and also a general hashtag to increase audience reach.

2. Choose a theme concept to enhance and maintain Brand Image. Themes that can be used can be obtained from many things, but the most important thing is to use a theme that fits the characteristics and also the message that is needed to convey to the Audience.

3. Create extraordinary content by applying photography techniques. This might be a challenge for coffee shops, because learning and applying photographic technical concepts is not easy. But over time, photography techniques will improve the quality of the content posted on the coffee shop's Instagram account. In addition, by knowing the basics of photography, learning videography for content can become easier.

For further research, it is recommended to carry out an Instagram reels analysis of the attractiveness value of content. This has not been explicitly discussed in the writing of this final project and it is possible that this will help the coffee shop. Especially to understand the attractiveness of Instagram Reels for coffee shop.

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